

BUILDING THE FOUNDATION FOR GEODETIC EXCELLENCE IN AFRICA

WORK PACKAGE 2 REPORT ON ASSESSMENT OF THE GEODETIC INFRASTRUCTURE AND HUMAN CAPACITY IN AFRICA

FEBRUARY 2026

Executive Summary

The role of Geodesy is fundamental to various scientific areas and essential for delivering services to people, households, and businesses. The objective of the project “*Building the Foundation for Geodetic Excellence in Africa*” through the Africa-UK Physics Partnership seeks to lay the groundwork for a comprehensive understanding and enhancement of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa. This was achieved through the assessment of the current state of geodetic equipment, computational infrastructure and human capacity across African nations as detailed in this report.

The Geodetic Infrastructure and Human capacity assessment in Africa was accomplished using desktop review, site visits to some select countries and administration of two distinct questionnaires; one on infrastructure and the other on human capacity.

The findings reveal that about 89% of African countries have continuously operating reference stations (CORS) while information about the same in 11% of the countries is lacking. About 91% of assessed CORS are government owned while 9% are privately owned. In terms of services, 64% of the CORS provide free service, 11% of the CORS provide paid for services and the service of the CORS 25% are unknown.

Africa has only one functional VLBI and Lunar Laser Ranging Stations and is located in South Africa. Three countries in Africa have stations belonging to the global DORIS network. As for reference frames, most countries have national geodetic reference frames which are compatible with ITRF, while WGS 84 is the datum that is in widespread use across the African continent. The use of WGS 84 datum is most common in Central, West and North African regions. A good number of countries also use national reference frames tied to AFREF and ITRF. The software used in processing GNSS as well as providing services across the various African countries are varied and a combination of variety of the software are used in several countries. The software include, for example, Oinertia GNSS, Compass solutions, EoS GNSS, JAVAD GNSS, Tersus, SateGen, Geolantis, Geocaster, Gipsy X, Kordil, Geodesy Tools, Geodyn, Miraspaco and Optron among others.

The human capacity assessment revealed that most of the African institutions (universities and colleges) offer training in surveying and geospatial sciences, but most offer training at the bachelors’ degree level in such areas as cartography (23%), LIS (25%), GIS (26%) and surveying and geospatial sciences (26%). About 65% of the respondents indicated that they have more than average competency in data analysis and use of geodetic tools. However, the respondents identified the following areas as the training needs, in order of priority

- (i) CORS installation, maintenance and operation
- (ii) Design and operation of GNSS networks including data
- (iii) Geodetic Reference frames
- (iv) Geoid modelling.

The planned training workshops should therefore focus on the top four training needs identified above. This report informs the next phase of the “*Building the Foundation for the Geodetic Excellence in Africa*” project, which will simulate the type and deployment of new geodetic infrastructure to improve the current situation of geodetic infrastructure in Africa.

Acknowledgement

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ADOS-African Doppler Survey Project

AFREF – African Geodetic Frames

AMSAT- The Radio Amateur Satellite Corporation

BGRF-Burundi Geodetic Reference Frame

CAFREF - Central Africa Reference Frame

CNES- Centre National d’Etudes Spatiales

CORS – Continuously Operating Reference Station

DORIS- Doppler Orbit Determination and Radio-positioning Integrated by Satellite

EAFREF - East Africa Reference Frame

ECA-Economic Commission for Africa

EGNOS-European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service

ELD79-European Libyan Datum

ESA-European Space Agency

ESPG- European Science Park Group

ETRS-Ethiopian Geodetic Reference Frame

GAGE- Geodetic Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience

GIS – Geographic Information Systems

GGOS- Global **Geodetic** Observing System

GNSS – Global Navigation Satellite Systems

GoK-Government of Kenya

GPS-Global Positioning System

GRS80-Geodetic Reference System 1980

HartRAO- Hartebeesthoek Radio Astronomy Observatory

IGAD – Intergovernmental Authority on Development

IGS – International GNSS Service

ITRF – International Terrestrial Reference Frame

ITRS– International Terrestrial Reference System

KENREF-Kenyan Geodetic Reference Frame

LGRF-Liberian Geodetic Reference Frame

LIS – Land Information System

NAFREF – North Africa Reference Frame

NGD-Nigerian Geodetic Datum

NIGNET-Nigerian Geodetic Network

NOAA- U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

PSMSL-Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level

RGRF-Rwandan Geodetic Reference Frame

RRS-Senegalese Geodetic Reference Frame

SADC - Southern African Development Community

SAFREF - South Africa Reference Frame

SDGs – Sustainable Development Goals

SANSAUNECA – United Nations Economic Commission for Africa

SLR/LLR-Solar and Lunar Laser Ranging

SPSS- Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

TAREF-Tanzanian Geodetic Reference Frame

UGRF-Uganda Geodetic Reference Frame

UN-United Nation

UTM-Universal Transverse Mercator

VLBI – Very Long Baseline Interferometry

WAFREF - West Africa Reference Frame

WGS84 – World Geodetic Systems

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.0 The Geodetic Infrastructure Outlook in Africa

1.1: Introduction

Geodesy is the science of accurately measuring and understanding the Earth's shape, orientation in space, and gravity field. Its role is fundamental to various scientific areas, such as cadastral surveying, mining, navigation and mapping, climate change, engineering, meteorology, and natural hazards, agriculture, precise orbit determination, crust deformations and space weather monitoring. The precise geographical coordinate reference systems produced by geodesy are essential for delivering services to people, households, and businesses, administering land rights and development permits, and developing and maintaining national and regional infrastructures to access water, waste management, electricity, transport, schooling, health facilities, markets, and security. As a result, geodesy contributes to the following Millenium Development Goals:

Key SDG Contributions:

- **SDG 13: Climate Action:** Crucial for monitoring sea-level rise, ice sheet changes, and other climate indicators.
- **SDG 15: Life on Land:** Supports monitoring of land degradation, ecosystem changes, and environmental protection.
- **SDG 2: Zero Hunger:** Enables precision agriculture to optimize crop production and resources.
- **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities:** Essential for disaster risk reduction (earthquakes, volcanoes), managing urban infrastructure, and ensuring safe navigation (GNSS).
- **SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure:** Provides the, precise, and sustainable global geodetic reference frame needed for engineering and mapping

However, the status of geodetic infrastructure on the African continent has not yet been fully documented and in fact, there are many different national and regional reference systems across the continent, a scenario which hampers smooth infrastructure development across borders, trade and even natural resource management.

The objective of the project “*Building the Foundation for Geodetic Excellence in Africa*” through the Africa-UK Physics Partnership seeks to address the above challenges by laying the groundwork for a comprehensive understanding and enhancement of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa. It will assess the current state of geodetic equipment, computational infrastructure and human capacity across African nations. The project provides a platform to establish a comprehensive and sustainable geodetic infrastructure across Africa, enabling the continent to contribute actively and benefit from global geodetic initiatives. This will be achieved through the following actions:

1. Conducting a thorough assessment of existing geodetic infrastructure, computational resources, and human capacity across African nations.
2. Developing strategic plans, supported by simulations, to place and enhance geodetic infrastructure in Africa.
3. Building a skilled cohort of early-career African geodesists through training, workshops, and international collaborations.
4. Laying the groundwork for establishing GGOS Africa, a regional affiliate coordinating geodetic activities across the continent.
5. Leveraging platforms like the UN Science Summit to raise awareness among policymakers and the public about the importance of geodesy in sustainable development.

The assessment of existing geodetic infrastructure, computational resources, and human capacity across African nations is implemented in **Work package 2**. The methodology used in this endeavour includes:

- (i) **Data collection:** Development and distribution of surveys to collect data on existing geodetic infrastructure, including GNSS stations, VLBI stations, and data processing centres. Conduct site visits to verify the data and assess the infrastructure's operational status.
- (ii) **Computational infrastructure assessment:** Evaluation of the availability and effectiveness of computational resources, including software tools and data processing capabilities. This will include assessing the knowledge and skills of local staff in using these tools.
- (iii) **Human capacity assessment:** Assessment of the current level of expertise in geodesy and related fields, identifying gaps in knowledge and training needs.
- (iv) **Data analysis:** Analysis of the collected data to identify strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement. The study will also highlight regions with critical infrastructure gaps.

The deliverables are the following:

- (a) A detailed inventory report of existing geodetic and computational infrastructure.

(b) An assessment report identifying gaps and needs in human capacity.

1.2 Situational Analysis

Africa is home to about 1.5 billion people as of the year 2025. Five of the top ten fastest growing economies in 2025 are from Africa. These are: South Sudan, Libya, Senegal, Sudan, Uganda and Niger. In 2025, Sub-Saharan Africa is projected to be the region with the fastest-growing mobile phone subscriber base. This growth is driven by a young, digitally-inclined population and increased investment in digital infrastructure. Despite these remarkable feats in progress, Africa faces numerous challenges in its development quest, some of which are related to climate change, geohazards mitigation, national mapping and surveying, spatial planning among others. The application of geodetic data and techniques have diverse applications in Africa, with impact in the following areas:

- (i) **National Mapping and Surveying:** Providing a foundation for accurate mapping and surveying activities.
- (ii) **Infrastructure Development:** Supporting the planning and construction of infrastructure projects.
- (iii) **Geohazards Mitigation:** Monitoring earthquakes, volcanic activity, and other natural hazards.
- (iv) **Resource Management:** Aiding in the exploration and management of natural resources.
- (v) **Scientific Research:** Facilitating research in areas like geodynamics, plate tectonics, and climate change.

A uniform coordinate reference frame is fundamental for any project, application, service or product that requires some form of geo-referencing. All georeferencing requires a uniform coordinate reference frame, yet each of the 54 countries in Africa has its own geodetic reference frame. In addition, some countries have more than one reference frame based on different datums. This patchwork of reference systems and frames in Africa makes it difficult to co-ordinate planning and development activities within countries and across national boundaries. However, the need for creating a unified geodetic reference frame for Africa was identified in 1879 [United Nations Economic and Social Council, *The African Geodetic Reference Frame*, E/ECA/GiSS/17/06, 2017]. Since then, four major efforts to create or to support the creation of a unified geodetic reference frame for Africa were put in place, starting with the measurement of the 30th Arc of Meridian between 1879 and 1954 and then moving on to the 12th Arc of Parallel between 1967 and 1971 and finally the African Doppler Survey (ADOS) project between 1982 and 1986. Ironically, it was the earliest measurement of the 30th Arc of Meridian without the use of modern technology such as electronic distance measuring equipment and navigation satellite positioning techniques that achieved the greatest success as far as creating a unified reference frame for Africa albeit only along the route of the 30th Arc of Meridian where the Arc 1950 and Arc 1960 or

variations of them are still used. After these efforts, the African Geodetic Reference Frame (AFREF) was conceived in the year 2000 to unify Africa's horizontal reference frames.

With the use of modern positioning technology such as Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), GNSS derived coordinates are now leveraged to make national coordinate systems upon which national surveying and mapping products and services are based. Many countries around the world, including some in Africa, are therefore updating, or are considering the updating of these national reference systems to be compatible with the global reference system and the GNSS reference system in particular. The International Terrestrial Reference System (ITRS) and its realization, the International Terrestrial Reference Frame (ITRF) (see Figure 1 below), is the global terrestrial reference system officially adopted by the International Association of Geodesy (IAG) and since 2012 and in 2016, the IAG established GGOS to handle such matters following the UN General Assembly Resolution on Reference Frames. The World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84), the reference system of the GPS which is the oldest and most widely used of the GNSS is virtually coincident to ITRF at the centimeter level and for all practical purposes WGS84 and ITRF, from ITRF08 onwards. In spite of using the common GNSS technology to upgrade at the national level, there remain slight variations of the reference frames used for GNSS derived co-ordinates depending on when upgrades are done. To rectify this situation, there are a number of efforts to create uniform reference frames regionally such that cross border infrastructure projects, mapping, border definition and so on are all based on a uniform modern regional geodetic reference frame. The existing global infrastructure of permanent Continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS) operated and maintained by the International GNSS Service (IGS) with voluntary contributions from over numerous self-funded agencies and research institutions provides high quality GNSS data, products and information resources which have supported the first 2013 realization of a uniform African continental reference system.

Figure 1: The locations of GNSS geodetic receivers in Africa. The pink line is the geomagnetic equator³

The locations of CORS stations used for ITRF in Africa

The Geodetic GNSS stations are now used for variety of applications such as geodynamics, meteorology, space weather among others. The figure 2 below captures the locations of GNSS geodetic receivers in Africa [Baki et al., 2023]

Figure 2: The locations of CORS stations used for ITRF in Africa

CORS STATIONS IN AFRICA PER COUNTRY

Figure 3: CORS stations per country

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 The Geodetic Infrastructure: Current Status and Future Requirements

Geodetic infrastructure provides accurate information about fundamental properties of the Earth as they change over time and has led to many scientific, civil, military, and space applications. The geodetic infrastructure consists of two principal components: (1) the network of observation instruments for each geodetic observation technique; and (2) associated international services composed of the various scientists, technicians, and administrators that support each technique. This chapter describes the current status of the main geodetic networks, the Earth observation satellites that underpin those networks, and the international services that support them as well as future technological and organizational needs in each of these areas:

Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI); GNSS/GPS; Satellite and Lunar Laser Ranging (SLR and LLR); DORIS.

2.1. Geodetic Networks

2.1.1. Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI)

VLBI is a geometric technique that employs radio telescopes located thousands of kilometers apart to observe natural radio sources that are located billions of light-years from the Earth, such as quasars¹. Although the observations from these telescopes are useful for radio astronomy, they also have important applications for geodesy. Because the radio sources are at such extreme distances, they appear fixed in space and provide the most stable celestial reference frame (the reference frame that does not rotate relative to distant stars and is centered at the Solar system's center of mass) that currently can be defined. As a result, VLBI is the definitive technique for tracking changes in the orientation of Earth in space, including precession, nutation, Earth rotation and, when VLBI is combined with Global Navigation Satellite Systems/Global Positioning System (GNSS/GPS) measurements, polar motion. The VLBI infrastructure includes the radio telescopes ("VLBI observatories") and central data processing facilities called correlator centers. Each technique also has an associated international service that is a critical component of the infrastructure. The International VLBI Service is an international collaboration of organizations that operate or support VLBI infrastructure (Schlüter and Behrend, 2007).

¹ The Geodetic Infrastructure: Current Status and Future Requirements." National Research Council. 2010. Precise Geodetic Infrastructure: National Requirements for a Shared Resource. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. doi: 10.17226/12954.×

Figure 3: The global network of the International Very Long Baseline Interferometry Service telescopes²

Note that the circles with black outlines in Figure 3 above indicate sites where next-generation VLBI Global Observing System instruments will be, or are already, located³. At the moment, African has only one functional VLBI station and it is located in South Africa. Another VLBI station was installed in Nigeria and is expected to start operation in March 2026.

2.1.2. GNSS/GPS

Global Navigation Satellite System System (GNSS) is now ubiquitous in civilian life, but it also provides a critical component of the geodetic infrastructure. GNSS operates by broadcasting predetermined coded signals, including predicted satellite positions from multiple dedicated satellites, and then correlating those signals with internally-generated versions of the same signals inside GNSS receivers on the ground or in other platforms, such as vehicles, ships, planes, or spacecraft. This correlation is used to measure the distances between the satellites and the receivers; given prior knowledge of satellites' positions in space, the user's time and position are subsequently determined with respect to the terrestrial reference frame (e.g., WGS 84 or ITRF). For more precise applications, geodetic GPS receivers track the carrier signal directly in addition to the codes, enabling measurements with a precision of a few millimeters. The existing GNSS infrastructure may be broken down into three segments: Space segment- maintain the system and

² National research foundation, south African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO) website:

<https://www.sarao.ac.za/about/hartrao/hartrao-research-programmes/astronomical-vlbi-at-hartrao/>

³ [A. L. Parker , L. McCallum, W. E. Featherstone, J. N. McCallum, and R. Haas, The Potential for Unifying Global Scale Satellite Measurements of Ground Displacements Using Radio Telescopes, Geophysical Research Letters, 11841-11849; 10.1029/2019 GL084915

generate broadcast satellite orbital position and timing data (i.e., ephemeris); ground control-infrastructure that has been installed primarily to address scientific questions; and user-networks that have been installed to support civil engineering and surveying projects.

The latency of data distribution from these networks varies between real-time transmissions of data to several month-long lags for scientifically important locations lacking easy communications links.

There are thousands of GNSS receivers distributed around the world, and the sizes of the networks controlled by single entities vary greatly. The Operational Control Segment network used to generate the broadcast ephemeris data for civil and military navigation is probably the smallest but most secure.

Two major developments are occurring that will affect future applications of these GPS networks: (1) there is an increasing trend toward real-time access to high-sample rate data (one hertz and higher); and (2) new GNSS satellites are being developed that will add many more satellites and data types to the existing constellations. The transition to real-time data collection and dissemination is driven largely by the surveying community and industry, which can use real-time data to increase productivity in the field and improve vehicle tracking and navigation on local and global scales, respectively. In addition, the scientific community can use these data for developing warning systems for tsunamis and volcanic eruptions. It is expected that more GPS stations will be converted to real-time operation to support these types of activities. These new real-time applications affect the costs of network operations because they require continuously-operating data streams and the archival of high-rate data streams. On the other hand, real-time data are valuable for multiple uses, providing a broad community that can support the costs of these networks.

The other development that will affect existing GNSS/GPS networks is the transition from GPS-only receivers to combined GNSSreceivers. GNSS receivers observe multiple constellations of satellites to provide precise positioning, navigation, and timing. GNSS receivers can track signals from four major global systems - GPS, GLONASS, BeiDou and Galileo. Receivers are now readily available and deployed for commercial applications.

The IGS model promotes continuous innovation and improvement of product quality; as such, a service-oriented approach is needed to address development and operation of the GNSS networks and the national geodetic infrastructure in general.

2.1.3. Satellite and Lunar Laser Ranging (SLR and LLR)

Laser ranging is a technique used to measure the time it takes for ultra-short laser pulses to reach retroreflector arrays on satellites or the moon and reflect back to Earth. The laser pulse is focused to a narrow beam by a telescope aimed at a satellite or the moon, and the return signal (in some cases as low as a single photon) is captured by the same telescope or by a larger, more sensitive

parallel telescope (see Figure 4). Because the laser beam is so narrow, the orbits of the satellites or the moon must be predicted accurately and the telescopes must be pointed precisely in order for the telescopes to track their targets. Unlike radiometric techniques like VLBI, laser ranging only can operate when the sky is clear or through very thin clouds. However, the optical frequencies are much less susceptible to refraction from water vapor in the atmosphere. The precision of laser ranging has improved from a few meters in 1964 to a few millimeters today with centimeter-level absolute ranging accuracy. Achieving ranging accuracy at the millimeter level is an important challenge as the laser ranging community strives to improve the quality of the data.

SLR stations are operated by a variety of institutions around the world that cooperate to provide a global tracking data set for approximately 30 satellites. Laser ranging data and analysis activities are managed by the International Laser Ranging Service (Pearlman et al., 2002). Most of the collected data are available within an hour of acquisition. Laser ranging data are used to define and maintain the ITRF (Altamimi et al., 2007), to observe temporal variations of Earth's gravity field (Cox and Chao, 2002; Cheng and Tapley, 2004), to determine Earth and lunar-orientation parameters and other fundamental physical constants for Earth, and to perform tests of general relativity (Ciufolini and Pavlis, 2004). Laser ranging also has provided a 30-year history of geodetic information (long-wavelength gravity, geocenter, and plate motion), is used to determine or verify centimeter-precision satellite orbits (Exertier et al., 2001), including ongoing altimeter (ERS-2, GFO, Jason-1, Jason-2, and ICESat) and gravity (CHAMP, GRACE) missions; and continues to provide long-wavelength gravity variations to supplement gravity missions such as GRACE.

LLR is currently performed at stations in Apache Point, New Mexico, Grasse, France, and McDonald Observatory, Texas. However, the Apache Point station, which was designed for millimeter-level accuracy is in limited operation. The Grasse site has recently restarted lunar observations after being out of operation for several years for upgrades and refurbishment. An SLR station in Matera, Italy is capable of lunar ranging but has not yet initiated a lunar observing program. In addition to performing LLR using two-way ranging to the retroreflector arrays on the moon, experiments have begun that are attempting one-way laser ranging to the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter.

An ongoing concern with the SLR network is the lack of uniform coverage and performance. Roughly 80 percent of the SLR tracking on the LAGEOS satellites (used for determining the ITRF) is from the northern hemisphere, and only about a third of the total tracking is from the western hemisphere. Furthermore, tracking can vary greatly from station to station depending on weather conditions and staffing resources. Among the stations that provided more than 100 passes for the Jason-1 altimeter satellite during 2007, the U.S. sites all fall in the lower half. Increasing the data yield from lower-volume sites, filling in the gaps in the SLR tracking network, and improving the overall balance in the station distribution are critical goals for the SLR system. In addition, the SLR network is threatened by reductions in operations or outright station closures due to considerable operation costs. The segment of the global SLR network that is operated by the United

States is at risk of failure because the physical infrastructure is aging and many of the trained personnel in its small workforce are nearing retirement age.

Several significant enhancements are required for the next generation of SLR systems to improve data quality and reduce the cost of operation. Perhaps the most important needed improvement is to make the tracking equipment capable of fully autonomous operation yet retain the ability to acquire tracking for satellites up to GNSS/GPS altitudes. A prototype for such a system has been developed and is being tested at the Goddard Geophysical and Astronomical Observatory in Greenbelt, Maryland (a “fundamental” site where multiple geodetic techniques are co-located). In addition, multi-kilohertz firing rates, improved epoch timing, more stable ranging calibration, and operating in the single photon regime will reduce random and systematic errors for laser ranging. New applications of next-generation laser tracking stations include kilohertz-scanning of satellite surfaces (to determine the spin axis and rotation rate of spherical satellites) and atmospheric seeing measurements along the laser beam (to provide information on atmospheric turbulence). Kilohertz time transfer techniques are currently being tested on the Jason-2 mission with the Time Transfer by Laser Link (T2L2) experiment where one picosecond stability over several minutes may be achievable.

To enable lunar and interplanetary applications there is also a need to upgrade more laser ranging stations to lunar ranging capability, and progress should continue in the area of laser transponders to the moon and other planets.

2.1.4. Doppler Orbit Determination and Radio-positioning Integrated by Satellite (DORIS)

The DORIS system is a French civil precise orbit determination and positioning system. DORIS consists of a network of terrestrial beacons that transmit signals to instruments onboard a satellite including an antenna, radio receiver, and an ultra-stable oscillator that provides the reference frequency standard. The onboard receiver compares the signal emitted by the ground beacon against the onboard frequency standard. Because of the satellite’s velocity, the incoming signal will appear to be shifted in frequency causing a “beat” with respect to the satellite’s internal clock. Measurements of the number of beat cycles can be used to determine the velocity of the satellite, which is then incorporated with satellite orbit dynamics to determine the distance between the satellite and the ground beacon. DORIS is optimized for precise orbit determination with global coverage and all-weather measurements. The system was designed and developed by the Centre National d’Etudes Spatiales (CNES, the French Space Agency) in partnership with the Groupe de Recherche de Géodésie Spatiale (the French space geodesy research group) and the Institut Géographique National (the French national mapping agency). It was developed primarily for precise orbit determination of altimeter missions and, consequently, also for geodetic ground station positioning. The DORIS products and activities are managed by the International DORIS Service (IDS) (Tavernier et al., 2006).

Figure 4: A map showing the locations of current DORIS ground based beacons. The network shows well-balanced nodes in both the Northern and Southern Hemispheres. (Source IDS, 2018)

The DORIS ground segment currently consists of 57 beacons with a remarkably uniform coverage around Earth (See Figure 4). This even coverage was established in part, because in the early development of the system, interference would occur within the receiver if the transmitters were close to each other. The new receivers, however, no longer have this limitation and can track several beacons at the same time. Nevertheless, CNES has strived to distribute the beacons evenly for the best possible performance for satellite orbit determination. One of the advantages of DORIS is that all observations are collected centrally onboard the satellites and no ground links are necessary making it possible to deploy beacons in remote and inhospitable areas (for example, islands in the southern hemisphere and Antarctica). As the ITRF attempts to achieve a no net rotation system, sites distributed over many locations on different plates is important. The scientific contributions of DORIS also increase as the time span increases providing a useful “lever arm” for station velocity determination. Some DORIS sites have been occupied since the early 1990s. The DORIS network is constantly being maintained with renovations at many of the sites to upgrade the transmitters or improve the stability of the antennas.

The DORIS network is well distributed, and the commitment of CNES to the maintenance of the system appears to be strong. Currently, there are six satellites carrying DORIS receivers, and it has been demonstrated that the DORIS positioning performance improves significantly when using four or more satellites (Altamimi and Collilieux, 2010). Consequently, installing the DORIS system on more satellites will significantly improve the DORIS contribution to positioning and geodesy applications.

2.2. MEASURING EARTH'S GLOBAL GRAVITY FIELD

Actual gravity measurements using terrestrial, satellite (GRACE/GOCE/CHAMP), airborne and shipborne has dramatically improved the ability to measure Earth's global gravity field. Prior to the GRACE mission, the resolution of the gravity field from space was limited to relatively long wavelength.

Theoretical gravity, computed using different equations based on normalized ellipsoid have been used to defined the value of gravity for a perfectly smooth oblate Earth. From the theoretical gravity values, the “gravity anomaly”, which is a measure of how actual gravity deviates from this idealized value has been used to generate maps of the anomalies to reflect the changes in the Earth's mass distribution, particularly in the crust, revealing many features associated with plate tectonics.

For more detailed gravity maps, terrestrial gravity data must be incorporated. Over land, expensive surface gravity surveys must be conducted. Over the oceans where the sea surface conforms closely to the Earth's gravity field at the shorter wavelengths radar altimeter satellites have provided detailed information⁴.

2.2.1 Tide Gauges

The global tide gauge network is important for geodesy in several respects. Historically, tide gauge data helped in defining geodetic reference heights (“datums”) at country scales. Recall that elevation or orthometric height is defined relative to mean sea level. In addition, tide gauge data provide information on ocean tides and long-term variations in sea level. Tide gauge data are especially critical for calibrating in-orbit altimetric satellites. For example, using a set of about 50 high-quality tide gauges distributed around the world Mitchum (1998) detected an artificial drift in the TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter caused by an algorithm error. Since then, drifts of instruments (in particular, radiometers used for measuring atmospheric water vapor) onboard altimeter satellites are routinely monitored by systematically comparing altimetry-derived and tide gauge-based sea level variations (see Mitchum, 2000; Nerem and Mitchum, 2001). Using GNSS/GPS-corrected tide gauges, Wöppelmann et al. (2009) estimated that regional sea level trends were different using the ITRF from the year 2000 versus the ITRF from the year 2005 due to the systematic differences between the two ITRF solutions.

The largest database of monthly and annual mean sea level records from tide gauges is the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL) (Woodworth and Player, 2003). Although the PSMSL includes data from approximately 2,000 sites in about 200 nations, the records are inconsistent in terms of data length and quality. Only about 10-20 percent of this data set is useable for long-term sea level studies. For oceanographic, climate, and coastal sea level research, a core network of 290 high-quality PSMSL stations has been designed and is called the Global Sea Level

⁴ Center for Space Research (CSR), The University of Texas at Austin, <https://www.csr.utexas.edu>

Observing System (GLOSS), which is coordinated by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (Woodworth and Player, 2003).

One of the primary uncertainties in tide gauge calibration is the vertical motion of the ground at individual tide gauges. Mitchum (1998) proposed to design a dedicated network of globally-distributed tide gauges with GNSS/GPS correction for land movement that would be able to detect altimeter drift errors of one millimeter/year for a three-year period. Since then, tide gauges have proven to be extremely useful for calibrating satellite altimetry systems. Nevertheless, accurate knowledge of vertical land movements at tide gauge sites is still lacking. A significant part of the 0.4-0.6 millimeter/year uncertainty in the altimetry-derived rate of global mean sea level rise comes from reference frame errors or from the lack of any measurement of the vertical motions of the tide gauges used for calibration (Nerem and Mitchum, 2001; Beckley et al., 2007).

In 2001, the International GNSS Service established a pilot project called TIGA (GPS Tide Gauge bench mark monitoring) (Bevis et al., 2002) with an objective of establishing the required research infrastructure (observing stations, data centers, and dedicated analysis centers) for determining vertical motions at tide gauges to an accuracy of better than one millimeter/year within a decade. Determining local vertical rates at such a level of accuracy remains challenging, however, partly because of challenges involved in maintaining the stability of the reference frame and maintaining frequent leveling (at least annually) between the GNSS/GPS antenna and the tide gauge in places where these are not closely co-located. Regular leveling surveys are often neglected over time, particularly in places where the distance between the two instruments is large. Where this distance is more than one kilometer leveling ties error can be large and become a significant part of the error budget. Thus, except for sites with well-established local or regional stability, GNSS/GPS stations more than one kilometer from the tide gauge cannot really be considered as co-located. In many cases the GNSS/GPS station may need to be located on or very close to the tide gauge to represent its vertical motion accurately

2.2.2 Terrestrial (Ground and Airborne) Gravity

Physical height systems based on the geoid or quasi geoid determine the direction of water flow. Thus knowledge of heights systems is critical for applications such as estimating floodplain extent, evaluating storm surge hazards, and designing aqueducts. At present, orthometric heights in the United States are determined by tying local surveys into a network of 600,000 leveling monuments, which were established over the past century by the NGS. This network was built up over decades using a variety of instruments and procedures with varying data quality and biases. That network has been steadily degrading as monuments are damaged or destroyed or experience unmonitored vertical motion. Today, leveling is a time-consuming, labor-intensive, and expensive surveying technique, and it is impractical to continue to maintain the existing monument network. Instead, the NGS has proposed that the United States switch to a method in which orthometric heights are determined using GNSS/GPS to measure geometric heights and then subtracting modeled geoid heights. This method is faster, less expensive, and more accurate than leveling. However, it requires an accurate, high-resolution geoid model.

The geoid is the level surface (a surface of constant gravitational potential) that, over the open ocean, approximates mean sea level. Extending the geoid to land was typically accomplished with ground-based leveling techniques, but is now augmented with global gravity field models from space techniques.

An accurate geoid is particularly important along the coastlines because many coastal areas are flat enough that small errors in height estimates can lead to mismodeled flood hazard predictions.

The geodetic community has recognized the potential of using highly precise gravity measurements to monitor vertical crustal motions and subsurface mass movements, particularly in combination with GNSS/GPS measurements of height changes (Wahr et al., 1995).

2.3. EARTH OBSERVATION SATELLITES

Artificial satellites are an essential component of the precise geodetic infrastructure. These satellites provide the link between the global reference frame and the end user of geodetic products. Indeed, without the satellite component there would not be an ITRF. The artificial satellites can be broadly divided according to the measurements they provide. GNSS satellites are used for precise point positioning anywhere on or near Earth's surface (including low-Earth orbit).

CHAPTER 3: GEODETIC INFRASTRUCTURE

3.0 Methodology

The methodology applied in this assessment was accomplished using desktop review, Country visits to some select countries in Africa, as well as the development and administration of two digital questionnaires. The two questionnaires addressed infrastructure and human resource capacity in Africa respectively. This assessment focuses specifically on gathering information on the current geodetic infrastructure and capabilities within Africa. This information will help to considerably build a sustainable geodetic reference frame for Africa. This study covers the information on GNSS/CORS in each as well as the information on coordinate reference systems in each country.

The human capital needs assessment focused on profiling the existing policy, geodetic infrastructure (hardware, software and data) and human resources required to utilize emerging geodetic technologies for enhanced analysis and understanding of key developmental issues. The human capital assessment will form the framework for intervention by the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) and its partners on geodetic framework for Africa. This human capital assessment covered each country's workforce in areas like education, skills, experience, and training related to geospatial and geodetic technologies, the current state of human capital within a country, training needs and gaps.

The field work for the work package 2 entailed study visits to selected countries where there was little information from the desk top study. During the visits geodetic sites were visited and face-to-face interviews conducted with key stakeholders on the geodetic networks mainly Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI), GNSS/GPS, Satellite and Lunar Laser Ranging (SLR and LLR), DORIS. The stakeholders included the relevant government agencies task with the establishment and maintenance of the geodetic networks such as National Mapping Agencies, practitioners who utilizes the data generate by the geodetic networks, the research institute mandated with the training of the human resource. In addition, documentary material and any secondary literature available have been collected.

The data collected has been analyzed and a report generated including a compilation of lessons learned to lay a foundation for further development of the Foundation for Geodetic Excellence in Africa.

The geodetic infrastructure provides accurate information about fundamental properties of the Earth as they change over time and has led to many scientific, civil, military, and commercial applications. Numerous agencies and organizations have made valuable contributions to the geodetic infrastructure over the past half century; however, in many countries in Africa, this critical infrastructure are not adequate and are now degrading from age and lack of maintenance from critical institution mandated with the oversight. Renewed investment in the geodetic infrastructure

is needed to maintain and modernize existing systems and to enable the development of sophisticated new applications with significant economic, national security, and scientific benefits

For the purpose of this assessments, key-informants included staff from relevant government departments in the respective countries, regulatory bodies, geodetic departments' staff, country geodetic networks, practicing geodesists and land surveyors, colleges and Universities dealing with land and geodesy, government agencies and mapping institutions. The respondents in the country training colleges and universities completed one questionnaire on geodesy training while the others completed the second questionnaire on geodetic infrastructure.

3.1. Assessment Tools

Two questionnaires (ANNEXES II-and III) were developed and digitized in order to provide relevant information concerning the assessment objectives and were sent to various key-informants by e-mail for completion.

The first questionnaire was created to assess the current geodetic Infrastructure and Capabilities within Africa to help in building a sustainable geodetic observations for Africa. The first questionnaire was structured according to the following scheme:

- Section A - General Information aimed at describing the respondent's profile.
- Section B – Information on the geodetic infrastructure within the respective countries
- Section C – Information on the coordinate reference systems within the respective countries

The second questionnaire was created to assess the current state of human capital in geodesy within a country, identify gaps, and inform strategies for development and improvement. The second questionnaire was structured according to the following scheme:

- Section A - Education and Training within the respective countries
- Section B – Technical Skills within the respective countries
- Section C – Training and Development Needs within the respective countries

The typology of questions included open, open-ended, closed-end and scaled response items rated according to 4 and 5-point scales, from 1 =No skill 2: Minimal skill 3: Moderate skill 4: Competent 5: Expert, rate the following technical skills within the context of your organization/Country in view of processing geodetic/geospatial data.

The following indicators were used to ascertain their usefulness, applicability and reliability of the questionnaires:

- Time needed for completing the interview;

- Clarity of questions;
- Validity in terms of providing the information required by the survey;
- Reliability in terms of providing consistent information.

The findings indicated that:

- The time required to complete the interviews was appropriate;
- Some questions were redundant;
- Most of the questions provided information were consistent with the purpose of the assessment.

Following these findings or redundant questions were rephrased or deleted and the final questionnaires were developed and digitalized.

3.2 Respondents

There was a total of 46 respondents to the questionnaire on geodetic infrastructure from 22 different countries (Table 3). There were 18 respondents from Directors of Government Departments, 16 from academic staff, 8 from licensed or registered practitioners while 3 were from the Chief Executive officers of private companies (Table 2).

Table 1: Summary of the Geodetic Infrastructure mapping respondents by type.

Respondent Type	Comments	No. of Respondents
Directors of Government Departments	e.g. Deputy Director/ Head of Survey and Hydrographic Services, Head of Government Agencies, Head of Mapping Sections etc.	18
Academic Staff	e.g. Lecturers, Senior Lecturers, Professors, Research Fellows	17
Practitioners	e.g. Registered Surveyors, Licensed Surveyors, Registered Engineers	8
Private Company CEOs	e.g. chief Executive officers of Agencies and Companies	3
		46

Table 2: Summary of the Geodetic Infrastructure mapping respondents by Country

S/No.	Country	No. of Respondents
1	Nigeria	8
2	Botswana	2
3	Burkina Faso	1

4	Cameroon	2
5	Comoros	1
6	Cote d'Ivoire	3
7	Ethiopia	4
8	Ghana	1
9	Kenya	4
10	Lesotho	2
11	Madagascar	1
12	Malawi	2
13	Mauritania	1
14	Rwanda	2
15	Senegal	2
16	Seychelles	1
17	Sierra Leone	1
18	South Africa	2
19	Tanzania	1
20	Togo	1
21	Tunisia	1
22	Uganda	3
Total		46

There were a total of 30 respondents to the the human capital questionnaire from 16 countries (Table 5). There wer 14 respondents from public universities, 1 from private university, 14 from government agencies while 1 was from an international organization (Table 4).

Table 3: Summary of the Human Capital mapping respondents by type

Respondent Type	Comments	Respondents
Public Universities	e.g. Universities, Survey Institutes, Institute of Land Administration, Institute of Cartography	14
Private Universities	e.g. Lecturers, Senior Lecturers, Professors, Research Fellows	1
Government Agencies	e.g. Land survey and physical planning departments, Topo Cadastre Unit, Directorate of Geographic Information Systems	14
International Organizations	e.g. Regional Mapping Agency	1
TOTAL		30

Table 4: Summary of the Human Capital mapping respondents by Country

S/No.	Country	No. of Respondents
1	Botswana	2
2	Burkina Faso	1
3	Cameroon	1
4	Comoros	1
5	Cote d'Ivoire	3
6	Ethiopia	3
7	Kenya	3
8	Lesotho	2
9	Malawi	2
10	Nigeria	3
11	Senegal	2
12	Sierra Leone	1
13	South Africa	1
14	Togo	1
15	Tunisia	1
16	Uganda	3
Total		30

3.3. Data Management

The completed questionnaires were numbered and archived for purposes of verification and filing. In compliance with Government of Kenya (GoK) best practices on data management and data protection, all documents and materials (hard and electronic copies) that are essential for

documentation and replication will be kept in archives at least five years. These documents and materials include:

- Originals of filled out questionnaires
- Screen formats (data entry program)
- Original and cleaned databases
- Data analysis programs
- Any other documents or materials that may be required for further understanding and replication of results.

3.3.1. Measures taken to ensure completeness and coherence of responses

All respondents were asked to complete the e-mail questionnaire independently or in a group. The filled questionnaires have all been checked for completeness and coherence.

3.3.2. Data Entry and Cleaning

The data was collected using KOBOL application and SPSS was used for data analysis. The database was checked for quality and completeness with some duplications resulting in loss of about 5% error in the database

3.3.3. Analysis

Data entry and analysis were done using SPSS statistical package and Microsoft Excel was used in order to produce the charts. As a first step open questions had to be put into categorical variables. In order to examine the distribution of the full set of responses for each closed-end question among the question's choices, frequency tables, and pie charts were then produced.

To enhance efficiency and achievement of the assessment objectives, a plan describing the process from data entry to data presentation was prepared to guide the process. It also served as a checklist to ensure delivery of a quality product

Descriptive analysis was used to compute frequencies, recoding of variables and running of cross tabulation.

Frequency counts, percentages as well as qualitative analysis techniques were the main statistical tools employed in analyzing the data generated through the questionnaires. A non-response to any item of the questionnaires was considered invalid and was left out of the analyses. The analyses of the two questionnaires were finally done.

3.3.4. Frequencies and recoding of variables

Basic descriptive statistics on frequencies was computed to assess the quality of data and to assist with recoding of categorical variables or grouping variables. Frequencies helped in identifying missing cases and cases that are too few. After running frequencies and recoding, cross tabulation was carried out.

3.3.5. Presentation of Analysis Outputs

Data outputs were organized by question and by the variables described in the expected outputs. This facilitated the assessment the data for report writing. During the process of writing the report, further analysis was carried out as needed. Tables, graphs and pie charts were created using the analysis outputs. The graphics were used to illustrate frequencies and therefore occurrences of events or activities.

3.4. Study limitations

3.4.1. Reaching sample size

Data collectors faced some difficulties reaching the intended respondents. Data was collected for approximately 8 weeks starting in mid-October 2025. The data collection team also encountered absent respondents in certain countries.

3.4.2. Logistical challenges

The data collection team was unable to collect data from all countries in Africa due to none response of the questionnaires and logistical challenges.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

4.0 Findings

This chapter presents general characteristics of the study as well as the findings of the geodetic infrastructure and human capital assessment. The findings are presented in two sections. Under the first section, mapping of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa are illustrated. The second section is dedicated to human capital assessment and training needs identified.

4.1. Source of information

A total of the 46 respondents to the questionnaire on geodetic infrastructure participated in the assessment. Figure 5 shows the composition of the respondents. They comprised of 18 Directors of Government Departments (39%), 17 academic staff (37%), 8 licensed or registered practitioners (17% while 3 were chief executive officers of private companies (7%) . It should be noted that the respondents were from 22 countries for the geodetic infrastructure assessment and 16 for the human capital assessment.

Figure 5: Sources of information for the geodetic infrastructure assessment

Figure 6 shows the composition of the respondents on the assessment of human capital who participated in the assessment. These comprised of 14 public universities (47%), 1 private university, (3%) 14 government agencies (47%) while 1 (3%) was an international organization.

Figure 6: Sources of information for the human capital assessment

4.1.1. Country distribution of the respondents

Figure 7 shows the distribution per country of the 46 respondents who participated on mapping of the geodetic infrastructure the assessment

Figure 7: Country distribution of the respondents to geodetic infrastructure assessment

Figure 8 show the distribution of the 30 respondents over the 16 countries that participated in the human capital assessment.

Figure 8: Country distribution of the respondents to human capital assessment

4.2. Geodetic Infrastructure in Africa

As mentioned in the literature review, the geodetic infrastructure comprises a vast array of ground and space-based equipment and data processing tools. This infrastructure is organized into networks focused on particular scientific needs; the following are the critical geodetic networks that operate at the global scale, and support the International Terrestrial Reference Frame.

- VLBI (Very Long Baseline Interferometry) uses radio telescopes to determine the position of the Earth in space.
- GNSS (Global Navigational Satellite Systems, a generic term for systems like the U.S. Global Positioning System (GPS) use ground-based receivers and satellites to determine the locations of points on the Earth's surface
- SLR/LLR (Satellite Laser Ranging and Lunar Laser Ranging) reflects laser signals off satellites or the moon to provide information about the Earth's surface and gravity field, and the moon's orbit.
- DORIS (Doppler Orbitography and Radiopositioning Integrated by Satellite) uses satellites and ground beacons to track the precise positions of satellites and measure the height of water in the Earth's oceans

In comparing the number of continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS) in the various Countries in Africa, 88% of the respondents indicated that there are CORS in the respective Countries while 12% of the respondents indicated that there are no CORS in their respective countries. Further, the assessment found out that, out of the existing CORS, 91% are developed, operated and maintained by the respective Governments while only 9% are developed, operated and maintained by private companies (Figure 9).

Figure9: Operation and maintenance of continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS) in the various Countries by government agencies

From the assessment, most (64%) of the GNSS/CORS services are offered by the government for free while 11% of the GNSS/CORS are paid services. 16% of the respondents were not sure if the GNSS/CORS services are free or not, while 9% indicated that the GNSS/CORS services are still under trial or incomplete hence charging for the service is yet to commence (Figure .

Figure10: Service charge for the GNSS/CORS Services in the respective Countries

According to the perception of the respondents, the majority (52%) of the existing CORS networks in Africa have an average distribution distance of 50Km to 100 Km, while about 11% of the CORS networks have a distribution of less than 50Km (Figure 11). The assessment also showed that the majority (62%) of the existing CORS networks in Africa follow standards, guidelines / best practices, while about 11% of the CORS networks do not follow standards, guidelines / best practices, 9% of the respondents were not sure of the average distance distribution of the CORS networks (Figure 12).

Figure11: Distribution Density of the CORS Networks in Africa

According to the respondents, the majority (62%) of the existing CORS networks in Africa follow International GNSS Service (IGS) standards, while about 11% of the CORS networks do not follow standards, guidelines / best practices. Similarly, according to the perception of the respondents, the 16% were not sure whether or not the existing CORS networks in Africa follow standards, guidelines / best practices, while about 11% indicated that some of the CORS networks follow standards, guidelines / best practices (Figure 12).

Figure 9 12: Percentage of CORS networks in Africa following standards, guidelines / best practices

Figure 13 shows Types of Geodetic and Positioning Service in African Countries. According to the respondents most (77%) of the African Countries assessed offer GNSS Reference Station Data for post processing in RINEX format followed closely by Single station RTK at 64% and VRS Network RTK at 41%. 20% of the countries have Geoid Models for heighting and 50% provide heighting services. Its only 6 nations (11%), Uganda, Tanzania, Malawi, Ethiopia, Mozambique and Namibia which have their gravity data going into the EGM2020 model thus providing gravity data for modelling of the Earth.

Figure13: Types of Geodetic and Positioning Service in African Countries

According to the assessment, the respondents were unable to determine the ideal number of GNSS/CORS in the respective countries. However, the majority (91%) of the respondents were in agreement that the African Countries have the capability to build new GNSS/CORS and to maintain the current existing GNSS/CORS stations Networks

Figure 14: Percentage of African countries capable of building and maintaining GNSS/CORS Networks

Table 6 shows the GNSS/CORS networks in Africa. This information was obtained form desktop reviews, field visit and questionnaires.

Table 5: GNSS/CORS stations Networks in Africa

Geodetic Infrastructure assessment in various African Countries					
No	Country	Organization/ Service Provider	Infrastructure	No. of Stations	Status
1.	Kenya	1. Kenya Power and Lighting Company	CORS	15	Active/Working
		2. Measurement Systems Limited (MUYA CORS)	CORS	16	Active/Working
		3. Oakar Services Limited	CORS	1	Active/Working
		4. Optron (Pty) Limited	CORS	1	Active/Working
		5. Geoid Technologies Limited	CORS	1	Active/Working
2.	Ghana	1. GMX Systems Ltd	GNSS STATIONS/CORS	27	Active/Working
		2. Association of License Surveyors CORS		8	Active/Working
		LiSAGNet		8	Active/Working
		3. Geo-Tech Systems Ltd/ GMX Systems Ltd /LISAGNet project	CORS	85	Not all are active
3.	Uganda	Government- (UGRF) Private - Eagle CORS/SURVNET	CORS	84 CORS Government – 40 Private- 46	GNSS Active Reference Stations
4.	Rwanda	1. Rwanda Geodetic Network	CORS	10	Active Reference Stations
5.	South Africa	1. TrigNet		58	In full operation
		2. HartRao GeoData	GNSS Base Stations	1	In full operation
			Geodetic VLBI	1	Stored
		3. Earthscope (previously UNAVCO)	RTK Correction Services		In full operation
		4. RTK2GO	RTK Correction Services		In full operation
6	Nigeria	1. Office of Surveyor General of Federation (OSGOF)	CORS	15	Active/Working
		2. MIGNET	CORS	11	Active/Working
		3. Sacredion			Active/Working
7	Egypt	1. Egyptian Surveying Authority (ESA)	CORS	40	Active/Working
8	Senegal	1. RTK2GO	RTK Correction Services		Active/Working
		2. IGS	RTK Correction Services		Active/Working
		3. Earthscope (previously NAVCO)	RTK Correction Services		Active/Working
		4. Centipede	RTK Correction Services		Active/Working
		5. Measurement Systems Limited	RTK Correction Services		Active/Working

Geodetic Infrastructure assessment in various African Countries						
No	Country	Organization/ Service Provider	Infrastructure	No. of Stations	Status	
		6. ArduSimple	CORS		Active/Working	
		7. EagleCORS Business	CORS		Active/Working	
		8. ComNav Technology	CORS		Active/Working	
9	Algeria	REGAT CORS	CORS	59	Active/Working	
		AL-CORS-Net	CORS		Active/Working	
		RTK2GO	RTK Services	Correction		Active/Working
		IGS	RTK Services	Correction		Active/Working
		Earthscope (previously NAVCO)	RTK Services	Correction		Active/Working
		Algeria National Mapping Organization			5	Active
10	Cameroon	RTK2GO	RTK Services	Correction		Active/Working
		IGS	RTK Services	Correction		Active/Working
		Earthscope (previously NAVCO)	RTK Services	Correction		Active/Working
		4. EagleCORS	CORS			Active/Working
		5. Muya CORS	CORS			Active/Working
11	Zimbabwe	1. Zimbabwe National Geospatial and Spacy Agency (ZINGSA)	CORS		24	Active/Working
		2. Muya CORS				Active/Working
12	Malawi	1. Malawi Rifting GPS Network (MRGN)	CORS			Active/Working
		2. Africa Array GPS Network (AAGN)	CORS			Active/Working
		3. Muya CORS	CORS			Active/Working
13	Tanzania	1. National Geo- information Centre	CORS			Active/Working
		2. EagleCORS	CORS			Active/Working
		3. ComNav Technology	CORS			Active/Working
		4. Muya CORS	CORS			Active/Working
14	Botswana	1. Cohensive Botswana (Proprietary) Limited	CORS		69	Active/Working
		2. EagleCORS	CORS			Active/Working
		3. Muya CORS	CORS			Active/Working
15	Angola	1. EDAS	GNSS STATIONS	14	Active	
			Correction Services			
16	Zambia	1. GMX Systems	CORS	26 Government - 19	Active	

Geodetic Infrastructure assessment in various African Countries					
No	Country	Organization/ Service Provider	Infrastructure	No. of Stations	Status
				Private - 7	
17	S. Sudan	1.ComNav Data Centre			
		2. IGAD Geodetic Reference Frame			
		3.CDC Net Software	RTK Correction Services		
18	Ethiopia	Ethiopian Space Science and Geospatial Technology (SSGi)	CORS	228	Active
		IGS	RTK Correction Service		Active
		Earthscope (previously NAVCO)	RTK Correction Service		Active
19	Rep of Congo	RTK2GO	RTK Correction Service		Active
		IGS	RTK Correction Service		Active
		Earthscope (previously NAVCO)	RTK Correction Service		Active
20	Libya	CORS-Libya	CORS	50	Active
21	Morocco	Morocco Network	CORS	4	Active
			GNSS Stations	9	Working
22	Sudan		CORS	2	Active
23	Madagascar	Status Unknown			Unknown
24	Namibia	Namibian Land Surveyors Organisation INTRIP	CORS Geodetic Network -	27	Active
25	Gambia				Unknown
26	Gabon				Unknown
27	Lesotho				Unknown
28	Eritrea	AFREF	None		Operational
29	Burundi	MUYA Hexagon RTK2GO	CORS RTK Correction Services RTK Correction Services		Active
30	Guinea				Unknown
31	Somalia				Unknown
32	Seychelles	RTK2GO NTRIP IGS Topnet Quectel	RTK Data Corrections		Active

Geodetic Infrastructure assessment in various African Countries					
No	Country	Organization/ Service Provider	Infrastructure	No. of Stations	Status
33	Tunisia	RTK2GO IGS Earthscope	RTK Correction Services CORS	3	Active
34	Comoros	RTK2GO ArduSimple PointPerfect			Unknown
35	Chad	RTK2GO IGS Earthscope	RTK Correction Services		Active
36	Congo	RTK2GO IGS EagleCORS ComNav Tech Earthscope	RTK Correction Services		Active
37	Ivory Coast	ChcNav NTRIP Protocol	RTK Correction Services		Active
38	Mozambique	Quectel Topcon RTK2GO	RTK Correction Services		Active
39	Mali	MUYA Hexagon PPP Correction ArduSimple	CORS RTK Correction Services RTK Correction Services		Active
40	Togo	Hexagon Quectel RTK2GO	RTK Correction Services		Active
41	Mauritania	Hexagon Quectel RTK2GO	RTK Correction Services		Active
42	Liberia	Terraster RTK2GO	RTK Correction Services		Active
43	Djibouti	SBAS ComNav Tech Swift Navigation Quectel RTK2GO EoS Positioning Systems	RTK Correction Services		Active
43	Mauritius	NovAlet's Terraster PointPerfect	RTK Correction Services CORS	2	Active
45	Sierra Leone	Trimble RTK2GO Hexagon			
46	Benin				Unknown
47	Cape Verde				Unknown
48	Guinea Bissau				Unknown
49	Equatorial Guinea				Unknown

Geodetic Infrastructure assessment in various African Countries					
No	Country	Organization/ Service Provider	Infrastructure	No. of Stations	Status
50	Burkina Faso	Skylark Topnet Live	RTK Correction Services		Active
51	Niger				Unknown
52	Swaziland	CheNav RTK2GO NTRIP Caster	RTK Correction Services		Active
53	Central African Republic	-			Unknown

Table 7 shows GNSS Correction Service providers and Software used in Africa countries.

Table 6: GNSS Correction Service providers and Software used in Africa

No	Country	GNSS Correction Services Providers	GNSS Software
1	Algeria	NTRIP Casters Hexagon ArduSimple	Qinertia GNSS Compass Solution Eos GNSS JAVAD GNSS
2	Angola	ArduSimple Quectel Hexagon Hemisphere Atlas	Septentrio Eos GNSS Tersus MIRASPACO
3	Burkina Faso	Hemisphere Atlas Hexagon	Eos GNSS Compass Solutions Tersus Qinertia
4	Burundi	Quectel ArduSimple Hexagon NTRIP	Compass Solutions SatGen Tersus PNW
5	Cameroon	NTRIP Casters	Compass Solutions Eos GNSS Tersus Software Qinertia GNSS
6	Cape Verde	Quectel Marinestar ArduSimple	Eos GNSS Tersus JAVAD RxTools
7	Chad	Marinester Qinertia SBAS ArduSimple Hexagon NTRIP	JAVAD Compass Solution Qinertia GNSS
8	Comoros	Hemisphere Atlas Hexagon NTRIP Quectel	Septentrio Tersus Qinertia Skydel

9	Djibouti	Hemisphere Atlas Hexagon NovAtel Quectel	Tersus GNSS Eos GNSS Skydel JAVAD GNSS
10	Egypt	NTRIP Casters Quectel ArduSimple Hemisphere	JAVAD GNSS Septentrio Qinertia
11	Eritrea	Hexagon Hemisphere Atlas Marinestar NovAtel	JAVAD GNSS SatGen Skydel Qinertia Qinertia
12	Ethiopia	SBAS Quectel Tersus	Septentrio Compass Solution Qinertia
13	Gabon	NTRIP Que ctel Ardu Simple	Compass Solutions Tersus JAVAD GNSS SatGen Skydel Geolantis.360
14	Ghana	Hexagon Hemisphere Atlas ArduSimple	Geocaster Eos GNSS Compass Solution
15	Guinea Bissau	Quectel NTRIP MArinestar	Tersus Eos GNSS Septentrio
16	Ivory Coast	NTRIP SpaceStar CHCNAV Xred-ppc	
17	Kenya	RTK2GO IGS NTRIP Earthscope	GipsyX Kordil Geodesy Tools (KGT) GEODYN Qinertia

18	Lesotho	ArduSimple Hexagon SBAS Quectel	Tersus Eos GNSS Compass Solutions
19	Liberia	Hexagon SBAS Hemisphere Atlas Quectel	Tersus Compass Solutions JAVAD GNSS Eos GNSS
20	Libya	Quectel Hexagon Sitech	Septentrio Qinertia RxTools
21	Malawi	Quectel AduSimple NTRIP	Compass Solutions Qinertia Tersus SatGen
22	Mali	Geode TM GNSS NTRIP Marine star ArduSimple	Septentrio Eos GNSS Compass Solutions Tersus
23	Mauritius	Quectel Marinestar NTRIP	Eos GNSS Tersus JAVAD GNSS
24	Morocco	NTRIP Casters	
25	Mozambique	SBAS AltraNav Marinestar Sitech SA NovAtel	MIRASPACO Eos Software Tersus
26	Muritania	Sitech SA Quectel	Kydell REDtoolbok Eos GNSS Qinertia
27	Namibia	Quectel ArduSimple Sitech Marinestar	Eos GNSS Compass Solutions RxTools Qinertia Tersus GeoBee

28	Niger	Quectel ArduSimple NTRIP SBAS	REDtoolbox Tersus Eos GNSS Compass Solutions
29	Nigeria	CHCNAV Hemisphere Atlas Quectel NTRIP	Tersus GNSS Eos GNSS Qinertia
30	Rwanda	Quectel	JAVAD GNSS Eos GNSS RxTools Geocaster
31	Senegal	ArduSimple Hemisphere Atlas NTRIP Quectel	Compass Solutions Septentrio Tersus PNW Software
32	Sierra Leone	NTRIP MarineStar NovAtel	SatGen Compass Solutions Qinertia
33	South Africa	Quectel NTRIP SITECH TrigNet	Tersus GNSS OPTRON
34	South Sudan	Quectel ArduSimple	Eos GNSS Tersus GNSS
35	Seychelles	SBAS NTRIP Hemisphere Atlas Sitech SA	Qinertia Septentrio SatGen JAVAD
36	Tanzania		Compass Solutions Tersus Eos GNSS Qinertia GNSS Septentrio

37	Togo	RTK2GO Ardu Simple	Eos GNSS Kydel GNSS Tersus PNW SatGen GNSS
38	Tunisia	ArduSimple Hemisphere Atlas Quectel SBAS NovAtel	Eos GNSS Compass Solutions SatGen Qinertia
39	Uganda	ComNav Quectel Hemisphere Atlas	M6 GNSS Eos GNSS Tersus RxTools
40	Zambia	Quectel NTRIP ArduSimple NovAtel	Eos GNSS JAVAD Tersus

Table 8 shows the geodetic reference used by different African countries, while Tble 9 shows the reference frames used in countries and number CORs stations in the se countries.

Table 7: Geodetic Reference frame used in the various African Countries

	Name of National Geodetic Datum	Reference Ellipsoid	Geodetic Reference Frame for the CORS	CORS network	coordinate list of CORS stations
Botswana	Botswana National Geodetic Reference System 2002	WGS84	ITRF2001	No	No
	Botswana Terrestrial Refence System (BTRS)				
Burkina Faso		GRS80	ITRF 2008, epoch 2011.7205 (21/09/2011: UT: 12h)	Yes	www. bfcors.net
					https://www.igb.bf
Cameroon	Cameroon Geodetic Reference System	GRS-80 (WGS84)	IRF2008 Epoch 2011.5		
Comoros					
Cote d'Ivoire	LE RGIR ; LE RGIO ; LE RGID QUI CONSTITUE LE SOCLE DE NOTRE INFRASTRUCTURE		ITRF 2014 EPOQUE 2010.0	Yes	GeoPortal Ivoirien
Ethiopia	Adindan	Clarke 1880/ WGS84		Yes	ADIS
Kenya	Arcdatum1960	Clarke1880	ITRF 2014	✓	www.isk.or.ge
	KENREF (KENYA GEODETIC REFERENCE FRAME)				
Lesotho	Cape Datum	Modified Clarke 1880	None	None	
Madagascar	Laborde Madagascar	Hayford 1924	None	None	
Malawi	Arc 1950 (Arc of the 30th Meridian 1950)	Clarke 1880 (Arc)	ITRF2008, ITRF2014	Yes	https://www.unavco.org/
Mauritania	Mauritania 1999	WGS84	ITRF2014 epoch 2021	None	
Nigeria	Minna Datum	Clarke 1880	ITRF 2008, ITRF 2020	Yes	www.nignet.gov
Senegal	Senegal RRS04	GRS80	ITRF2000 epoch 2004.5	Yes	https://geodesie.minfinances.sn/

Seychelles	SeyRef2019	WGS84	ITRF2014	None	N/A
Sierra Leone	SeyRef2019	WGS84	ITRF2014	None	N/A
South Africa	Hartebeesthoek94	WGS84	ITRF2014	Yes	www.trignet.co.za ftp://ftp.trignet.co.za/
Tanzania	Tanzania Reference Frame 2011	WGS84	iTRF2020	Yes	TAREF11
Togo	Togo geodetic reference	WGS84	ITRF2014 epoch 2021	Yes	cors.otr.tg
Tunisia	Nouvelle Triangulation Tunisienne NTT	Clarke 1880 IGN	ITRF00	Yes	Réseau GNSS Permanent Tunisien
Uganda	Uganda Geodetic Reference Frame	WGS84 (GRS80)	ITRF2005 epoch 2010	Yes	http://ugrf.mlhud.go.ug/

Table 8: National, Regional and Global Geodetic Reference Frames in Use in Africa

No	Country	Region	Geodetic Reference frame in Use	No of CORS Stations	Compatibility with ITRF
1	Kenya	Eastern Africa	Kenya Geodetic Reference Frame (KENREF)	18	ITRF 2000 but epoch not known.
2	Uganda	Eastern Africa	Uganda Geodetic Reference Frame (UGRF)	86	ITRF2005 epoch 2010.0.
3	Tanzania	Eastern Africa	Tanzanian Geodetic Reference Frame (TAREF)	21	ITRF2014, specifically at epoch 2011.0
4	Rwanda	Eastern Africa	Rwanda Geodetic Reference Frame (RGRF)	10	ITRF2000 but no known epoch
5	Burundi	Eastern Africa	Burundi Geodetic Reference Frame (BGRF)	Unknown	ITRF2014 at epoch 2010.0
6	Ethiopia	Eastern Africa	Ethiopian Geodetic Reference Frame (ETRS89)	224	European Terrestrial Reference System 1989 (ETRS89)
7	South Sudan	Eastern Africa	South Sudan Geodetic Reference Frame	Unknown	ITRF2008 (IGS2008) Epoch 2010.0
8	Somalia	Eastern Africa	Somalia Geodetic Reference Frame (SomRef)	10	ITRF 2014 epoch 2010.0
9	Djibouti	Eastern Africa	Djibouti Geodetic Reference Frame/WGS 84	Unknown	ITRF 2014 epoch 2010.0
10	Eritrea	Eastern Africa	WGS 84	Unknown	Linked to ITRF but no known epoch
11	Seychelles	Eastern Africa	WGS 84	1	ITRF 2014 epoch 2010.0
12	South Africa	Southern Africa	South African Geodetic Reference Frame (SAGRF)	57	ITRF 2014 epoch 2010.0
13	Namibia	Southern Africa	Namibia Geodetic Reference Frame -Schwarzeck/EPSSG codes 29333/AFREF	5	ITRF 2005 epoch 2005.0
14	Botswana	Southern Africa	Botswana Geodetic Reference Frame (BGRF)/WGS 84	23	ITRF 2008 epoch 2005.0
15	Angola	Southern Africa	Angolan Geodetic Reference Frame RSAO13	18	ITRF 2008 epoch 2012.9
16	Zimbabwe	Southern Africa	Arc 1950//UTM Zone 36S	25	ITR 2000 epoch 2000.0
17	Zambia	Southern Africa	Zambian Geodetic Reference Frame (ZGRF)	1	ITRF2014 epoch 2010.0
18	Mozambique	Southern Africa	AFREF/WGS 84	Unknown	ITRF94 epoch 1994.0
19	Eswatini	Southern Africa	Arc 1950	9	AFREF/ITRF but version and epoch not known
20	Lesotho	Southern Africa	WGS 84	Unknown	ITRF 2000 epoch 2004.0

21	Malawi	Southern Africa	Arc 1950	6	AFREF/ITRF epoch not known.
22	Mauritius	Southern Africa	Le Pouce 1934/ WGS 84	Unknown	ITRF 2000 epoch 2000.0
23	Madagascar	Southern Africa	Tananarive (Paris) / Laborde Grid	1	
24	Democratic Republic of Congo	Central Africa	RGRDC 2005/ WGS 84	Unknown	AFREF/ ITRF2008
25	Republic of Congo	Central Africa	GRS 1980 (GRS80)/AFREF	1	ITRF2014 but epoch not known
26	Central African Republic	Central Africa	AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch unknown
27	Equatorial Guinea	Central Africa	WGS 84	11	ITRF2014 but epoch not known.
28	Gabon	Central Africa	Cape Esteiras 1955 Datum/WGS 84/ AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch unknown
29	Cameroon	Central Africa	WGS 84	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch unknown
30	Chad	Central Africa	RGT20	Unknown	Not known
31	Sao Tome and Principe	Central Africa	WGS 84	Unknown	ITRF2014 but epoch not known
32	Nigeria	West Africa	Nigerian Geocentric Datum (NGD2012)- Compatible with WGS 84	16	Alignment with ITRF but version and epoch not known
33	Ghana	West Africa	ITRS	8	ITRF05 epoch 2007.39
34	Benin	West Africa	WGS 84 /AFREF	7	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
35	Cote d'Ivoire	West Africa	RGCI 2022//ITRF2014 epoch 2010.0	Unknown	ITRF2014 epoch 2010.0
36	The Gambia	West Africa	WGS 84/ AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
37	Liberia	West Africa	LGRF2021	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
38	Sierra Leone	West Africa	Sierra Leone 1968 with EPSG codes 4175/ WGS 84/AFREF	13	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
39	Niger	West Africa	WGS 84/ AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known

40	Mali	West Africa	WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N/ AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
41	Togo	West Africa	WGS 84	Unknown	ITRF2020 but epoch not known
41	Guinea- Bissau	West Africa	WGS 84/ AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
43	Mauritania	West Africa	WGS 84/ AFREF	Unknown	ITRF2008 at epoch 2012.0.
44	Senegal	West Africa	RRS04 based on ITRF2000	5	ITRF2000 but epoch not known
45	Burkina Faso	West Africa	WGS 84 / UTM zone 30N/ AFREF	9	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
46	Cape Verde	West Africa	WGS 84 / Cape Verde National, with the EPSG code 4826.	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
47	Guinea	West Africa	Conakry 1905 and Dabola 1981 / WGS 84	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
48	Algeria	North Africa	Nord Sahara 1959 (NS-59)/ RGS2020 / UTM zone 29N/ AFREF	189	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
49	Egypt	North Africa	WGS 84/ ITRF94 (epoch 1996)	40	ITRF2008 epoch 2011.8096
50	Libya	North Africa	ELD79 (European Libyan Datum 1979) and LGD2006 (Libyan Geodetic Datum 2006) /WGS 84 / AFREF	Unknown	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
51	Morocco	North Africa	WGS 84/ Merchich datum, identified by EPSG code 4261/ AFREF	17	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
52	Sudan	North Africa	ITRF2008 (IGS2008)	Unknown	ITRF2008 epoch 2005.0
53	Tunisia	North Africa	Carthage, often referenced as Carthage, referenced as EPSG:4223 or EPSG:2088 (Carthage / TM 11 NE)/ WGS 84/ AFREF	23	Compatible with ITRF but version and epoch not known
54	Western Sahara	North Africa	Merchich / Sahara Nord (EPSG:26194)/ European Datum 1950 (ED50)/WGS 84	Unknown	Not linked to ITRF

4.3. Human Capacity in Geodesy

4.3.1. Education and Training

Geodesy and geomatic training institutions (universities and colleges) play a critical role in strengthening geodetic systems by producing skilled, multidisciplinary, and multi-sectoral geospatial teams. According to the assessment of the human capital in geodetic sciences, several universities across Africa offer specialized education in geomatics, geoinformatics, geospatial engineering, surveying, GIS, and remote sensing

Figure 15 illustrates the following as key training areas in geodetic sciences in Africa; Cartography (23%), LIS (25%), GIS (26%), and Surveying/ Geospatial/ Geodesy (26%). The key training levels as shown in Figure 16, are Certificate (6%), Diploma (13%), Bachelors (34%), Masters (29%) and Doctorate (18%).

Figure15: Training areas in geodetic sciences in Africa

Figure 10: Key training levels in geodetic sciences in Africa

The universities in 25 countries that provide training in various geodetic sciences and at different levels are detailed in Table 9.

Table 9: Universities in Africa offering specialized education in Geomatics, Geospatial Engineering and GIS

No.	Name of Country	Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered					Level of training offered				
			Cartography	Geodesy / LIS	GIS	Surveying/ Geomatics/ Geospatial	Others	Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (M.sc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate
1	Algeria	University of Constantine 1(Frères Mentouri)		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		National Polytechnic School of Algiers (ENP)		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
2	Benin	Centre Régional de Formation pour Entretien Routier (CERFER – Benin)	✓		✓	✓				✓		
3	Botswana	University of Botswana	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓		
		Botswana College of Engineering and Technology	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓			
		China University of Geosciences			✓						✓	
		Queensland University of Technology	✓							✓		
4	Burkina Faso	Ecole Nationale des Travaux Public (ENTP)	✓	✓	✓	✓					✓	
		Ecole supérieure des Travaux publics de Ouagadougou (ESTPO)	✓	✓	✓	✓					✓	
		Université Joseph Ki-ZERBO				✓					✓	✓
		Lycée technique de Ouagadougou	✓						✓			
		Institut Géographique du Burkina (IGB)			✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		Centre Régional de Formation pour Entretien Routier (CERFER – Burkina Faso)	✓		✓	✓				✓		
		Ecole supérieure de la Jeunesse	✓	✓	✓						✓	
5	Cameroon	University of Yaoundé	✓	✓		✓	✓				✓	
		University of Dschang	✓	✓		✓					✓	
		YIMGA Higher Institute		✓		✓	✓			✓		
6	Comoros	University of Comoros					✓			✓		
7	Côte d'Ivoire	CURAT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

No.	Name of Country	Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered					Level of training offered				
			Cartography	Geodesy / LIS	GIS	Surveying/ Geomatics/ Geospatial	Others	Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (M.sc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate
		INPHB	✓			✓			✓	✓	✓	
		Université Félix Houphouet Boigny d'ABIDJAN		✓		✓				✓		
		Centre Régional de Formation pour Entretien Routier (CERFER – Côte d'Ivoire)	✓		✓	✓				✓		
		Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire (UVCI)		✓					✓		✓	
		Lycee professionnel de SAN PEDRO	✓						✓	✓		
		École Supérieure Africaine des TIC					✓		✓	✓	✓	
		Université Alassane Ouattara (Bouaké)		✓					✓		✓	
		Institut de Géographie Tropicale		✓		✓			✓		✓	
		Institut National Polytechnique Félix Houphouet Boigny de YAMOUSSOUKRO	✓						✓	✓	✓	
8	Egypt	Ain Shams University				✓				✓	✓	✓
		German University of Cairo		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	
9	Ethiopia	Adama science and Technology university	✓		✓					✓	✓	
		Addis Ababa University	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		Bahir dar University		✓	✓					✓	✓	✓
		Bahir Dar polytechnic college			✓				✓			
		Ambo University			✓					✓		
		Civil service University	✓		✓						✓	
		Debre Birhan University	✓							✓		
		Debre Markos University	✓	✓	✓					✓		
		Dire Dawa University	✓							✓		
		Hawassa University		✓						✓		
Oda Bultu University	✓		✓					✓				

No.	Name of Country	Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered					Level of training offered				
			Cartography	Geodesy / LIS	GIS	Surveying/ Geomatics/ Geospatial	Others	Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (M.sc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate
		Matu University	✓		✓						✓	
		Mekelle University	✓							✓		
		Space Science and Geospatial Institute	✓	✓							✓	✓
		Wollega University	✓							✓		
		Woldia University	✓							✓		
10	Ghana	University of Ghana			✓						✓	
11	Kenya	University of Nairobi		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
		Technical University of Kenya		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
		Jomo Kenyatta University of Science and Technology			✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		Taita Taveta University			✓						✓	
		Dedan Kimathi University			✓	✓					✓	✓
		Regional Center for Mapping of Resources and Development	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓			
		Ramogi Institute of Advance Technology (RIAT)	✓			✓		✓	✓			
		Tom Mboya University				✓					✓	
		Mawego Institute	✓			✓		✓	✓			
		Eldoret National Polytechnic	✓			✓		✓	✓			
		Sigalagala National Polytechnic	✓			✓		✓	✓			
		Kabete National Polytechnic	✓			✓		✓	✓			
		Jeremiah Nyaga Polytechnic	✓			✓		✓	✓			
Kenya Institute of Surveying and Mapping (KISM)	✓			✓			✓					
12	Lesotho	National University of Lesotho		✓		✓				✓		
13	Libya	Libya International University		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	
14	Malawi	Mzuzu University	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
		University of Malawi – The Polytechnic	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	

No.	Name of Country	Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered					Level of training offered				
			Cartography	Geodesy / LIS	GIS	Surveying/ Geomatics/ Geospatial	Others	Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (M.sc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate
		University of Malawi – Chancellor College		✓					✓	✓		
		Malawi University of Science and Technology (MUST)	✓		✓				✓	✓		
		Malawi University of Business and Applied Sciences (MUBAS)	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓		
		Natural Resources College (NRC)	✓	✓		✓		✓				
		Lilongwe University of Agriculture and Natural Resources (LUANAR)	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓		
		Blantyre Technical College	✓					✓				
		Lilongwe Technical College	✓					✓				
		Zomba Technical College	✓					✓				
		TEVETA-Accredited Technical Colleges (Various)	✓					✓				
15	Mali	National School of Engineering (ENI-ABT), Bamako		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓		
16	Nigeria	University of Lagos	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
		University of Nigeria	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
		University of Benin BENIN CITY NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
		University of Abuja	✓						✓			
		University of Ilorin	✓						✓			
		Obafemi Awolowo University ILE IFE NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓			
		Ahmadu Bello University ZARIA NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		
		Anambra State University AWKA NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
		Federal School of Surveying, Oyo	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
		Federal University of Technology MINNA NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		

No.	Name of Country	Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered					Level of training offered				
			Cartography	Geodesy / LIS	GIS	Surveying/ Geomatics/ Geospatial	Others	Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (M.sc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate
		Federal University of Technology AKURE NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	
		Federal University of Technology OWERRI NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	
		Rivers State University PORT HARCOURT NIGERIA	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
		Yaba College of Technology	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
		Kaduna Polytechnic				✓			✓			
		Several Institutes	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			
17	Rwanda	University of Rwanda				✓				✓	✓	
18	Senegal	Université Iba Der Thiam de Thiès (UIDT)	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓
		Université Sine Saloum El Hadji Ibrahima Niass		✓						✓	✓	
		Université Amadou Matar Mbow		✓						✓	✓	
19	Sierra Leone	Njala University	✓	✓		✓				✓	✓	
		Ernest Bai Koroma University		✓							✓	
20	South Africa	University of Cape Town	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		University of Pretoria			✓						✓	
		University of Kwazulu Natal			✓						✓	
		Stellenbosch University	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		Durban University of Technology			✓	✓				✓	✓	
		Cape Peninsula University of Technology	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
21	Sudan	Sudan University of Science and Technology		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	
		University of Khartoum	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		University of El Gezira	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
22	Tanzania	Ardhi University			✓	✓				✓	✓	

No.	Name of Country	Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered					Level of training offered				
			Cartography	Geodesy / LIS	GIS	Surveying/ Geomatics/ Geospatial	Others	Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (M.sc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate
		University of Dar es Salaam			✓						✓	
23	Togo	University of Lome		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
		FORMATEC University	✓							✓		
		University of Kara	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓	
		National Institute of Agriculture	✓							✓		
		Ecole Supérieure d'Architecture et de Topographie au Togo (ESTABAT)	✓							✓		
		Centre Régional de Formation pour Entretien Routier (CERFER – Togo)	✓		✓	✓				✓		
24	Tunisia	University of Mjez ElBab	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓		
		ISET Tozeur		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	
		Ecole Supérieure Privée d'Application et de Technologie (ESAT)		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	
25	Uganda	Kyambogo University	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓		
		Ndejje University	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓		
		Makerere University	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
		Kabale University	✓							✓		

According to the respondents, the main areas of specialization practiced in their respective countries were identified as cadastral surveying (18%), topographic surveying (13%), engineering surveying (7%), Geodesy (6%), GNSS (5%), GIS (19%), Cartography (10%), photogrammetry (5%), remote sensing (7%) and land administration (8%). According to the respondents, 95% of the African countries have professional certifications or licenses related to geospatial science and practice.

This study also assessed the competency level of the respondents in the Likert scale of 1 to 5: 1= No skill; 2=Minimal skill; 3=Moderate skill; 4 = Competent; and 5: Expert within the context of your organization/ Country in view of processing geodetic/ geospatial data. Figure 17 shows proficiency in using various geodetic software. More than 50% of the respondents are expert or competent in the use of geodetic software. Most respondents (over 70%) are expert or competent in the use of surveying instruments as shown in Figure 18. A smaller percentage (about 55%) are proficient in geodetic datums, coordinate systems and projections (Figure 19)

Figure 17: Proficiency in using various geodetic software

Figure18: Proficiency in operating various surveying instruments

Figure19: Proficiency on geodetic datums, coordinate systems, and projections

The ability of respondents to perform geodetic data analysis and interpretation was a critical aspect of this assessment. The respondents indicated their competency and the competency of their organizations to analyze and interpret data in a geodetic context. The assessment provided the results shown in Figure 20. where about 65% of the respondents say that their organizations are expert or competent in their ability to perform data analysis and interpretation in geodetic context.

Figure 0: Ability to perform data analysis and interpretation in a geodetic context

4.3.2. Training and Development Needs

The assessment also looked into the skills or knowledge gaps in Surveying/Geospatial/Geomatic science. In almost all the countries assessed, the training courses available include the university programs, short professional courses, on-the-job training within government departments, and limited regional workshops supported by international partners.

According to the assessment (Figure 21), the knowledge gaps and priority training needs that emerge as per the perception of the respondents were CORS installation, maintenance, and operation (18%), Design and operation of GNSS networks including data processing (15%), Geodetic Reference Systems (13%), Geoid modelling (12%), Space geodesy techniques (global geodetic observing systems)—such as VLBI, SLR, LLR, and DORIS (11%), Emerging technologies like UAVs, LiDAR, and cloud-based GIS (9%), Use of new surveying tools and scientific software (7%), Coding, Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning (6%), Computation of transformation parameters of ITRF and national datums (5%) and lastly Geodetic network adjustments and analysis (4%).

Figure21: Top 10 Priority Training Needs in Geodetic Science

On the type of training most effective for the respondents, the assessment established that most (50%) of the respondents preferred blended trainings with some being face-to-face and others being online trainings. A paltry (7%) of the respondents preferred purely online trainings while 43% of the respondents preferred only face-to-face trainings (Figure 22)

Figure 22: Types of training methods most effective for the respondents

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Introduction

This assessment will help considerably to build a sustainable geodetic reference frame for Africa. This study covers the information on geodetic infrastructure as well as information on coordinate reference systems in each country. The human capital needs assessment, on the other hand, focused on profiling the existing policy, geodetic infrastructure (hardware, software and data) and human resources required to utilize emerging geodetic technologies for enhanced analysis and understanding of key developmental issues. The human capital assessment will form the framework for intervention by the Global Geodetic Observing Observatory (GGOS) and its partners on human capacity development for geodesy in Africa.

5.2. The Geodetic Infrastructure in Africa

The findings on the current status of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa is expected to support the GGOS international services and organizational needs in Africa in VLBI, GNSS/GPS, Satellite and Lunar Ranging (SLR and LLR) and DORIS infrastructure.

Currently Africa has only one functional VLBI station and it is located in South Africa. Another VLBI station was installed in Nigeria and is expected to start operation in March 2026. Only three countries in Africa, South Africa, Gabon and Djibouti, have stations belonging to the global DORIS network.

Satellite and Lunar Laser Ranging (SLR/LLR) in Africa is primarily centered at the Hartebeesthoek Radio Astronomy Observatory (HartRAO) in South Africa, which operates the continent's only active International Laser Ranging Service (ILRS) station, MOBLAS-6. A major initiative is underway to develop a combined, high-precision lunar and satellite ranger at HartRAO to improve Southern Hemisphere and Africa in general, which is underrepresented

There are thousands of GNSS/GPS Network stations distributed around the various African Countries, majority of which are coupled by CORS networks, 91% of which are controlled by Government agencies while a paltry 9% are controlled by private entities. The majority of the GNSS/CORS service are free of charge in most (66%) of the African countries sampled.

According to the perception of the respondents, the majority (89%) of the existing CORS networks in Africa follow standards, guidelines / best practices, while about 11% of the CORS networks do not follow standards, guidelines / best practices hence can be improved and linked to the global networks. The majority of the countries need to work on improving the density of the GNSS station which currently averages 100 to 200km. This will bring down the distribution density to less than 50Km.

The GNSS/CORS networks operate under different datums, however majority of the Countries use WGS84 as the official datum for the GNSS/CORS networks.

5.3. Human Capacity in Africa

The assessment on human capital in geodesy revealed that GIS and surveying form the major components of the trainings offered in Africa with the certifications being dominated at Bachelors and Masters degrees levels. The assessment also established that most Universities in Africa offer specialized education in Geomatics, Geospatial Engineering and GIS. According to the assessment, 95% of the African countries sampled, have professional certifications or licenses related to geospatial science and practice and have personnel with sufficient proficiency in:

- using various geodetic software
- operating various surveying/geodetic instruments
- geodetic datums, coordinate systems, and projections
- performing data analysis and interpretation in a geodetic context

The findings on the human capital assessment revealed that the top five gaps and training needs that emerged as per the perception of the respondents were CORS installation, maintenance, and operation (18%), Design and operation of GNSS networks including data processing (15%), Geodetic Reference Systems (13%), Geoid modelling (12%), Space geodesy techniques (such as VLBI, SLR, LLR, and DORIS (11%).

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The objective of the *Building the Foundation for Geodetic Excellence in Africa* project through the Africa-UK Physics Partnership, seeks to address the above challenges by laying the groundwork for a comprehensive understanding and enhancement of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa. Work package 2 of the project was tasked with the assessment of Africa's geodetic infrastructure starting with the current state of geodetic equipment, computational infrastructure as well as assessment of the human capacity across African nations. The task of the work package 2 has been accomplished through desktop research and field data collection, leading to the generation of this report.

This assessment of Africa's geodetic infrastructure and human capacity across African nations report is the final report of the work package 2. It underlines the current status of the geodetic infrastructure in African Countries, the relevance and contribution of the geodetic networks to GGOS, and the effectiveness, relevance and efficiency of their links to Africa and globally.

This study has highlighted the various reference frames being used in African countries and, the training capacity, the training gaps as well as the expertise required in processing the geodetic data is hindering the current operation of the CORS networks in the African countries. The human capital assessment revealed that the top five training gaps and needs that emerge as per the perception of the respondents were CORS installation, maintenance, and operation, Design and operation of GNSS networks including data processing, Geodetic Reference Systems, Geoid modelling and Space geodesy techniques such as VLBI, SLR, LLR, and DORIS.

African countries need to develop and increase the density of the GNSS/CORS stations to reduce the average distances between stations to less than 200km. African countries are encouraged to use and integrate these CORS in their Real Time National geodetic frameworks including generating RTK and DGNSS solutions for wider applications to support their national development

African countries also should thrive to ascertain that the GNSS/CORS networks follow the standard guidelines. African countries should also work towards designing regional CORS networks to optimize the design of national networks and harmonize the GNSS/CORS datums across the regions

There are already existing curriculums for human capacity development in geodesy by various universities in Africa. It is necessary to compare the content of these curriculums with the findings of the training needs gaps identified by this assessment to see if they address the top five gaps and training needs that emerge from the assessment. Capacity development programmes need to be put in place in the areas where gaps and needs have been identified.

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Annex 1: Work Package 2 Members

Name	Institution	Email	Role on the project
Prof. Paul Baki	TUK		Work Package 2 Lead
Prof. Hussein Farah	TUK		Contributor
Dr. Godfrey Ogonda,	TUK		Contributor
Mr. Isaac Odera	TUK		Contributor
Mr. Ochieng Melli	TUK		Contributor
Dr Alet de Witt	HartRAO/DSI		Contributor
Prof. Roelf Botha	SARAO/TUT		Contributor

Annex 2: The QUESTIONNAIRE ON MAPPING GEODETIC INFRASTRUCTURE IN AFRICA

Key informant Questionnaire

GGOS, the Global Geodetic Observing System, aims to integrate the networks of permanently installed GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) receivers that provide real-time positioning data for various applications in Africa. GGOS-Africa is working to incorporate networks and other geodetic infrastructure in Africa into the global reference frame to support scientific research, surveying, and other geospatial applications

This Questionnaire seeks to gather information on the current GNSS CORS Infrastructure and Capabilities within Africa. This information will help considerably to building a sustainable geodetic reference frame for Africa

RESPONDENT INFORMATION

1.1. Name of respondent:

1.2. Designation of the respondent:

1.3. Email:

1.4. Telephone Contact:

1.5. Country:

1.6. Organisation or Agency (Name):

1.7. Type of Organisation or Agency:

- Government / Gouvernement
- Academia / Universitaire
- Commercial / Commerciale
- Other:

GNSS CORS

2.1 – Is the National government responsible for building and maintaining the national geodetic Infrastructure in your country/ state?

- Yes
- No

2.2 - Are there national and openly available Continuously Operating Reference GNSS Stations (CORS) installed in your country?

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

2.3 - In your country, which agency/agencies, private companies, etc (if any) provides positioning services, such as real time corrections, data streaming or online processing and GNSS reference station data?

- Private company

- Government
- I'm not sure
- Others: specify _____

2.4 - Are there permanent/semi-permanent GNSS stations or passive benchmarks that are occasionally measured by the national government?

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

2.5 - Does your country (through a national geodetic agency or any organization) provide the following geodetic and/or positioning services? Check all that apply.

- DGNSS
- Single Station RTK
- VRS Network RTK
- GNSS Reference Station Data (RINEX) for post processing
- Marks and Nodes
- Coordinates or Post-processing
- Heights
- Gravity data
- Geoid model

2.6 - Does your country (through a national geodetic agency or any organization) charge the geodetic and/or positioning services provided?

- No, it's free
- Yes, charges a fee
- I'm not sure
- Other specify

2.7 - Does your country Member State have the capability to build new and maintain its current GNSS CORS stations?

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

2.8 - What is the average spacing (distance) between these GNSS CORS stations? (one choice only)

- Less than 50 kms
- Between 50 and 100 kms
- Between 100 and 200 kms
- More than 200 kms
- I'm not sure

2.10 - Do the CORS monuments follow standards, guidelines / best practices? (choose only one)

- Yes

- Some stations
- No
- I'm not sure

2.11 - What CORS monument standards or guidelines or best practices does your country use? Check all that apply

- National
- International
- Other
- I'm not sure

Provide More Information about this standards, guidelines or best practices:

Upload 1 supported file: spreadsheet. Max 10 MB/ Add file

COORDINATE REFERENCE SYSTEM

3.1 – What is the name of the official datum\reference frame of your Country?

3.2 – What reference ellipsoid does your country use in the definition of the official datum?

3.3 – What geodetic reference frame and epoch are the CORS stations coordinated (e.g. ITRF2014 epoch 2010)?

3.4 - Does your country's CORS network(s) have a name(s) and website that you can share with us?

3.5 – Please provide a coordinate list of CORS station in your country?

Upload 1 supported file.

CLOSING STATEMENT

Thank you for responding to this Questionnaire on the GNSS CORS Infrastructure and Capabilities within Africa. This information will substantially help to build a sustainable geodetic reference frame for Africa.

Annex 3: QUESTIONNAIRE ON HUMAN CAPITAL IN GEODESY/GEODETIC SCIENCES

Key informant Questionnaire - Institutions

The **BUILDING THE FOUNDATION FOR GEODETIC EXCELLENCE IN AFRICA** project in conducting a human capital needs assessment on the status of geodesy in Africa at the Country Levels. This is being done by profiling the existing policy, geodetic infrastructure (hardware, software and data) and human resources to utilize emerging geodetic technologies for enhanced analysis and understanding of key developmental issues. The information provided in this interview guide will form the framework for intervention by the Global Geodetic Observing Stations (GGOS) and its partners on geodetic framework for Africa. This human capital assessment questionnaire in geodesy is intended to evaluate a country's/state's workforce in areas like education, skills, experience, and training related to geospatial and geodetic technologies. The questionnaire aims to capture ~~understand~~ the current state of human capital within a country and identify skills gaps, as these will ~~and~~ inform strategies for development and improvement.

RESPONDENT INFORMATION

1.1. Name of respondent:

1.2. Designation of the respondent:

1.3. Email:

1.4. Telephone Contact:

1.5. Country:

1.6. Organisation or Agency (Name):

1.7. Type of Organisation or Agency:

- Government / Gouvernement
- Academia / Universitaire
- Commercial / Commerciale
- Other:

SECTION II. Education and Training:

2.1. Which institutions/ colleges or universities in your country offer formal education in geospatial science (e.g., Bachelor's, Master's, PhD)?

Name of Institution, University or college	Degree program offered e.g. GIS, Geodesy, Geospatial Engineering, Surveying etc.	Level of training offered				
		Certificate	Diploma	Bachelors Degree	Masters (Msc, M.A)	PhD, Doctorate

2.2. What are the main areas of specialization within geospatial sciences that are dominant in your country (e.g., Surveying, GNSS, Geodesy, Remote sensing, GIS, Etc.)?

2.3. Are there any professional certifications or licenses related to geospatial science and practice?

Yes No. If yes, specify which ones:

2.4. Are there any specific training in areas relevant to Continuous Operating Reference Stations (CORS) (e.g., GPS, data processing etc.)?

Yes No. If yes, specify which ones:

2.5. Do you have a mentorship program for geospatial staff in your country?

Yes No. If yes, specify which ones:

SECTION III. Technical Skills:

In a scale of 1 to 5: 1 =No skill 2: Minimal skill 3: Moderate skill 4: Competent 5: Expert, rate the following technical skills within the context of your organization/Country in view of processing geodetic/geospatial data.

3.1. Rate your proficiency in using various geodetic software (e.g., AutoCAD, MicroStation, specialized geodetic software).

1		2		3		4		5	
---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--

3.2. Rate your proficiency in using various surveying instruments (e.g., total stations, GPS receivers).

1		2		3		4		5	
---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--

3.3. Rate your knowledge of geodetic datums, coordinate systems, and projections.

1		2		3		4		5	
---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--

3.4. Rate your ability to perform data analysis and interpretation in a geodetic context.

1		2		3		4		5	
---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--

3.5. Rate your ability to perform quality control and assurance on geodetic data.

1		2		3		4		5	
---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--	---	--

SECTION IV. Training and Development Needs:

4.1. What types of training in geospatial science would be most beneficial for your country?

4.2. What training resources are currently available in your country for geospatial scientists?

4.3. Are you satisfied with the training opportunities provided by your country?

4.4. What skills or knowledge gaps do you perceive in geospatial science?

4.5. What further trainings in geodesy are required for your country to support installation, operation and maintenance of CORs stations?

4.6. What types of training methods would be most effective for them?

- Face-to-face
- Online
- blended

Conclusion

We understand the sensitivity of sharing the information, and we are committed to safeguarding your data. The information you provide will remain confidential and secure. Your submission will only be used for non-commercial, research, and coordination purposes related to this initiative. We do not share your data with third parties without your explicit consent. Ownership of your data remains with you or your organization at all times.

Thank you for your participation

Annex 4: The Gantt chart

Building the Foundation for Geodetic Excellence in Africa project

Gantt Chart for Work Package 2

		2025												2026				
		Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	
Task/Activity																		
1	Identify one person to sit in the project oversight committee		█															
2	Identify key institutions to collaborate with work package 2 team in the assessment of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa	█	█															
3	Organize a consultative meeting with a team hired by the Kenya government to develop a strategy for the Kenyan geodetic system			█														
4	Develop a questionnaire for data collection					█												
5	Convert the questionnaire into a digital format such as KOBACOLLECT App or other similar applications						█											
6	Undertake a desktop review to understand the current status of the geodetic infrastructure in Africa					█	█											
7	Identify contact/liaison persons within the target countries							█	█									

8	Identify countries in which the WP2 team may need to acquire research licenses																	
9	Acquire research licenses in the identified Countries before data collection process																	
10	Conduct online and face-to-face key informant interviews (KIIs)																	
11	Prepare and submit a report on the Work Package 2 (WP2)																	
12	Conduct sensitization workshop for Policy Makers (2 Days)																	
13	Train early-career African geodesists through workshops in the Eastern, Southern & Central of Africa (5 Days)																	
14	Train early-career African geodesists through workshops for West and Northern Africa countries (5 Days)																	